

Metal-Chelates of 1-Amino-2-Naphthol

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Manuscript received 27 August 1974; revised 21 July 1975

Interactions between the carcinogenic ligand 1-amino-2-naphthol and the carcinogenic metal ions, Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pb(II), and U(VI), and the biologically important Ca(II), Mg(II), and Mn(II) have been investigated in 50% aqueous dioxan media at 30° and at various ionic concentrations, using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique. The thermodynamic stability constants of various species have been obtained by extrapolation of log *K* values to zero ionic strength. From the results the possible relations have been discussed between chelation and cancer.

MOST of the important biological systems e.g., vitamins, enzymes, and nucleic acids are attached to some metal ions and seem to be connected with cancer production. It has been postulated that the metal ions which are known to be carcinogenic are carried to the normal cell by the phenomenon of chelation with carcinogenic organic compounds which possess chelating structures initially or after metabolic alterations. These cations may replace the essential metal ions from the normal enzyme system or nucleic acids having similar electronic configurations. Sometimes the essential metal ions of one system in excess may also replace the essential metal ions of the other systems like the abnormal metals. The biological systems may also combine with metal-chelate replacing coordinated water molecule from the chelate. Thus abnormal metal ions and metal-chelates may change the mode of action of the normal enzyme systems or alter the structure and function of genetic materials by acting with nucleic acids, resulting in the formation of new associated protein (synthesis of polymeric nucleic acid) which cannot be controlled by the normal enzyme systems. The anticancer drugs also may deactivate the carcinogenesis by binding the abnormal (carcinogenic) metal itself or binding the abnormal nucleic acids *via* transition metal ions¹⁻⁶.

In connection with the studies from these laboratories on the chelation reactions of carcinogenic and anticancer compounds, the metal-chelates of folic acid⁷, riboflavine⁸, adenine⁹ and thioguanine¹⁰ have been described. Most of the compounds that cause, or those are used in, cancer therapy are chelating agents. It was thought of interest to investigate the behaviour of the chelating agent 1-amino-2-naphthol (AMN) which is known to cause cancer in the bladder. The metal ions chosen for the study were: Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and U(VI) which are carcinogenic, and Ca(II), Mg(II), and Mn(II) which are biologically active. The metal-AMN equilibria have been studied by

Bjerrum Calvin pH-titration technique in 50% aqueous dioxan media, AMN being sparingly soluble in water particularly in acidic media.

Experimental

Materials

All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled CO₂-free water. Metal nitrate solutions were obtained by dissolving nitrates of aluminium (III), chromium (III), manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II) and lead (II) in water; carbonates of beryllium (II), magnesium (II) and calcium (II), and metallic iron, in dilute nitric acid of known concentration. The metal contents were estimated by standard methods.

AMN-hydrochloride (Eastman Organic Chemicals) was dissolved in dioxan.

CO₂-free potassium hydroxide solution was prepared and was standardized against a standard solution of oxalic acid.

Procedure

For pH-titrations, sets of solutions of (i) nitric acid, (ii) nitric acid+AMN, and (iii) nitric acid+AMN+metal ion were prepared, such that the total volume was 50 ml and the final concentrations were $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ AMN, and $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal ion in each case. The titrant was 0.1016M KOH. The experiments were carried out at ionic concentrations of 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1; ionic strengths were maintained using KNO₃.

Measurements were carried out at 30° ± 0.01°.

From the titration curves, (Figs. 1a-d) the average number of protons associated with AMN ($\bar{n}_A$), average number of ligands attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$), and

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free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the formulae of Irving and Rossotti¹¹.

$$\bar{n}_A = y - \frac{(v'' - v')(N^\circ + E^\circ)}{(V^\circ + v')TC_L^\circ} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v''' - v'')(N^\circ + E^\circ)}{(V^\circ + v')\bar{n}_A TC_M^\circ} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^j \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } B} \right)^n \cdot V^\circ + v'''}{TC_L^\circ - \eta TC_M^\circ} \cdot \frac{1}{V^\circ} \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

where v' , v'' , v''' are the volumes of alkali required to reach the same pH in the acid, ligand, and chelate titration curves respectively; V° , TC_L° , TC_M° , E° are the volume of the mixtures, initial concentration of ligand, initial concentration of metal ions; initial concentration of acid; N° is the concentration of titrant; η is the number of dissociable protons; and β_n^H is the overall proton-ligand stability constant; B is the pH meter reading.

From the values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$, and pL ; formation curves were plotted and the formation constants were determined by the usual computational methods.

Results and Discussion

In the initial stages of the titration; the ligand curves shifted to the left of (or above) the acid curve due to the basic properties of the amino group, which accepts a proton from the strongly acidic medium. The protonated species formed dissociates in two steps as shown below :

The addition of alkali was accompanied by a gradual change of colour, both in the cases of the

ligand and the chelate. Initially in the acidic medium the colour of the ligand is yellowish red which gradually changes to red as alkali is added. In the metal-ligand systems also, the colour changed from yellowish red with increase of pH , the changes being identical in several cases with those of the ligand alone. The colour changes are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. CHANGES OF COLOUR WITH pH

System	pH	Colour
AMN	> 8.3	Yellowish red
	> 8.3	Red
Be(II)-AMN	> 8.3	Red
Mg(II)-AMN	> 8.3	Red
Al(III)-AMN	> 8.3	Red
Cr(III)-AMN	> 8.3	Red
Mn(II)-AMN	> 7.2	Yellow to greenish yellow
Fe(III)-AMN	> 5.0	Greenish yellow
Co(II)-AMN	> 6.85	Dark yellow
Ni(II)-AMN	> 8.3	Red
Cu(II)-AMN	> 5.5	Dark yellow
U(VI)-AMN	...	Yellowish red

It appears that the yellowish red colour is due to the protonated species, while red colour is due to the anion. In case of Mn(II) chelates, at pH 7.2 the value of $\bar{n} \approx 0.3$, which suggests the formation of 1:1 yellow species and the solution becomes greenish yellow with increase in alkali due to the formation of 1:2 species. The sharp colour change of Fe(III) systems from yellowish red to greenish yellow at pH 5.0 indicates the formation of 1:2 species ($\bar{n} < 1.0$ at pH 4.9, $\bar{n} > 1.0$ at pH 5.0). This sharp change of colour shows that the 1:1 and 1:2 species are independently formed which is confirmed from the shape of formation curves. The 1:3 species is also independently formed but the colour remains the same. At pH 6.8, $\bar{n} \approx 0.3$ for Co(II)-AMN system, and the colour change appears to be due to both the species 1:1 and 1:2 which coexist. The gradual colour changes from yellowish red to yellow are also accompanied by the shape of the formation curves. In the case of Cu(II)-AMN both the 1:1 and 1:2 species are yellow (at pH 5.5, $\bar{n} \approx 0.1$), and are independently formed as shown by the formation curves.

Ca(II) does not appear to react with AMN, since the ligand and chelate curves coincide. In Pb(II)-AMN the appearance of a precipitate at $pH \approx 3.4$ did not permit further studies.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were determined by various computational methods viz., (a) interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, (b) interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values, (c) use of mid-point, (d) correction term, and (e) least square treatment, whichever were applicable. The averages of the values obtained by the different methods are shown in Table 2 at various ionic strengths, i.e., 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1M.

TABLE 2. STABILITY CONSTANTS OF AMN CHELATES

Ionic strength	$\log K_n$	H ⁺	Be(II)	Mg(II)	Al(III)	Cr(III)	Mn(II)	Fe(III)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	U(VI)
0.10M	$\log K_1$	11.28	8.45	3.87	9.90	9.45	6.19	10.45	6.90	6.06	8.21	11.39
	$\log K_2$	3.97	5.71	3.80	7.86	8.28	5.87	8.59	6.14	5.30	5.89	6.89
	$\log K_3$	...	...	...	5.60	5.80	...	6.65	...	...	...	18.28
	$\log \beta_n$	15.25	14.16	7.67	23.36	23.53	12.06	25.59	13.04	11.36	14.10	11.48
0.05M	$\log K_1$	11.28	8.68	3.87	10.14	9.78	6.28	10.79	7.19	6.32	8.30	7.17
	$\log K_2$	4.00	5.74	3.80	8.46	8.30	5.91	8.73	6.22	5.33	6.16	...
	$\log K_3$	...	...	...	5.60	5.80	...	6.63	...	...	14.46	18.65
	$\log \beta_n$	15.28	14.42	7.67	24.20	23.88	12.19	26.15	13.41	11.65	8.32	11.61
0.01M	$\log K_1$	11.28	8.71	3.87	10.42	10.10	6.54	10.96	7.35	6.44	8.32	7.47
	$\log K_2$	4.04	5.84	3.80	8.86	8.38	5.86	8.88	6.40	5.36	5.82	...
	$\log K_3$	...	...	...	5.70	5.80	...	6.65	...	...	14.14	19.08
	$\log \beta_n$	15.32	14.55	7.67	24.98	24.28	12.40	26.49	13.75	11.80	8.30	11.65
→ 0	$\log K_1$	11.28	8.80	3.87	10.65	10.40	6.86	11.28	7.55	6.60	8.30	7.70
	$\log K_2$	4.10	5.90	3.80	9.45	8.40	5.86	9.00	6.52	5.39	5.80	...
	$\log K_3$	...	...	...	5.80	5.80	...	6.70	...	...	...	19.35
	$\log \beta_n$	15.38	14.70	7.67	25.90	24.60	12.72	26.98	14.07	11.99	14.10	...

FIG. Titration curves (30°; $\mu = 0.1M$)

- (a) ○ : Acid (A); ● : Ligand (L); y : Be(II)-L; ○ : Al(III)-L.
- (b) ○ : Acid (A); ● : Ligand (L); ⊗ : Mg (II)-L; ○ : U(VI)-L.
- (c) ○ : Acid (A); ● : Ligand (L); ● : Mn (II)-L; ⊗ : Cr(III)-L; Δ : Fe(III)-L.
- (d) ○ : Acid (A); ● : Ligand (L); ⊗ : Ni(II)-L; ⊗ : Cu(II)-L; ○ : Co(II)-L.

The thermodynamic values of stability constants were evaluated by extrapolation to zero ionic concentration from plots of $\log K$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$.

The titration curves show (Figs. 1a-d) that AMN does not form a chelate with Ca(II), whereas Mg(II) forms a chelate but above the physiological pH of 7.3. Consequently it may be concluded that nucleic acids or enzyme systems involving Ca(II) or Mg(II) would not be disturbed by the carcinogen AMN.

The $\bar{n}$ values show that maximum $\bar{n}$ is not attained at pH 7.3 in the cases of AMN chelates of Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II). This suggests that at least one coordination position remains unoccupied at the biological pH (7.3). This results in a combination with tissues easily, and may alter the normal enzyme or nucleic acid system to act as a carcinogen.

The stabilities of the metal-chelates of AMN are in the order :

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. N. Sinha, Department of Pathology, M.L.N. Medical College, Allahabad, for his interest.

References

1. A. ALBERT, *Pharmac. Rev.*, 1952, **4**, 136.
2. S. P. DATTA and B. R. RABIN, *Biochim. biophys. Acta*, 1956, **19**, 5724.
3. F. R. N. GURD and P. E. WILCOSE, "Advances in Protein Chemistry, Vol. 11, (Ed) by M. L. Anson, K. Bailey and J. T. Edsall. Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1956, p. 311.
4. A. HADDOW, "Ciba Foundation Symposium on Carcinogenesis, Mechanism of Action", Boston. Little Brown & Co., Wolstenholme, 1965, p. 300.
5. A. FRUST, "Chemistry of Chelation in Cancer", (Ed.) C. C. Thomas, Springfield, Illinois, U.S.A., 1963.
6. A. FRUST, *A Speculative Review. : Metal Binding in Medicine*, (Ed.), M. J. Seven, Lippincott, Philadelphia, 1963, p. 336.
7. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1970, **25b**, 1453.
8. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 109.
9. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1972, **27b**, 688.
10. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 98.
11. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.